

ROLE OF HIGH-RESOLUTION COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY IN THE EVALUATION OF DISEASE ACTIVITY IN PULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS

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Abstract

BACKGROUND

Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex mycobacterial species cause pulmonary tuberculosis. The majority of instances of mycobacterium tuberculosis are caused by this species; however, other species, such as *Mycobacterium africanum*, *Mycobacterium bovis*, *Mycobacterium microti*, and *Mycobacterium canettii*, can also produce a condition similar to this one. When a person with active tuberculosis coughs, sneezes, or speaks, tiny droplets of 1 to 5 μm in diameter can be released into the air and stay suspended for several hours. This is how airborne mycobacteria are spread.

OBJECTIVE

To evaluate the role of High-Resolution Computed Tomography in evaluation of disease activity in patients with pulmonary tuberculosis.

METHODOLOGY

This analytical cross-sectional study was carried out in the Hafizabad DHQ Hospital. The method of convenient sampling was applied. 55 patients with probable pulmonary tuberculosis who were referred from a chest X-ray to an HRCT chest were included in our four-month study. Following informed consent, data from 16 slices of the Toshiba CT was gathered.

RESULTS

There were 25 female patients and 30 male patients in our study. Approximately 50 years old was the average age at presentation. It was discovered that the presence of trees in buds (38.2%), ill-defined nodules (30.9%), and consolidation (40%) had a strong predictive value for identifying disease activity. There were related findings: ground glass opacity (7%), atelectasis (7%), and traction bronchiectasis (12%). The results indicated inactive disease: calcified granulomas (7%) and atelectasis (7%).

CONCLUSION

The HRCT has a higher sensitivity for distinguishing between active and inactive illness, it can be useful in both diagnosis and treatment. Consolidation, tree-in-bud look, and poorly defined nodules were the best markers of active illness. It was discovered that combining the indications increased the prediction value

INTRODUCTION

Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex mycobacterial species cause pulmonary tuberculosis. The majority of instances of mycobacterium tuberculosis are caused by this species; however, other species, such as Mycobacterium africanum, Mycobacterium bovis, Mycobacterium microti, and Mycobacterium canettii, can also produce a condition similar to this one.¹

Figures of lung involvement in people with active tuberculosis range from 79 to 87%. The lung is the most typically impacted tissue in the presence of tuberculosis in the immunocompetent host. In immune-compromised hosts, such as individuals affected with the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), estimates of lung involvement are

comparable. Research conducted between 1980 and 1990 suggested that the estimated rates of pulmonary involvement ranged from 70 to 92%.² On the other hand, extrapulmonary illness is also more common in these people. The lung serves as the entry point for tuberculosis in most cases. There are either little or no clinical signs or indicators at the time of initial contact with the bacterium. Usually, after being inhaled, the tubercle bacillus establishes an infection only in the lung's outermost region.² Globally, tuberculosis is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality, with Mycobacterium tuberculosis accounting for one-third of cases. Of these, 5-15% will experience active tuberculosis at some point in their lives.³

Caseating granuloma and cavitation are two pathologic manifestations of tuberculosis that arise from hypersensitivity that coexists with the host immune response that provides protection. The main type of cells infected by *M. tuberculosis* are macrophages.⁴ A prolonged, mucus-filled cough, pleuritic pain in the chest, hemoptysis, breathing difficulties wheezing, weakness or increasing fatigue, cachexia or weight loss, anorexia due to appetite loss, chills and a high body temperature, night sweats, and malaise are a few possible symptoms.⁵

Complications may be the initial sign of pulmonary tuberculosis. Pulmonary TB can result in a number of problems. They fall into the following categories: (a) Parenchymal lesions, such as scar carcinoma, aspergilloma, endstage lung deterioration, and thin-walled cavities (open negative syndrome). (b) Airway lesions, such as bronchiectasis, tracheobronchial stenosis, anthracofibrosis, broncholithiasis, and tuberculous laryngitis. (c) Vascular abnormalities such aneurysms like Rasmussen. (d) Pleural lesions, such as pneumothorax, Broncho pleural

fistula, empyema, pleural effusion, and dry pleurisy. (e) Chronic respiratory failure, secondary amyloidosis, and cor pulmonale are examples of general problems.⁶

The likelihood of contracting tuberculosis is contingent upon the likelihood of infection as well as the likelihood of infection progressing to active illness. The former will rely on how common tuberculosis is in the area in which the person works or resides. The latter will rely on a variety of individual-influencing factors, including genetic and environmental ones.⁷ There is a 5%–10% lifetime probability of the latent main complex reactivating in the normally immunocompetent. These estimates may be somewhat low for the majority of individuals with latent tuberculosis infection who are not reexposed to Mtb, as they were created prior to the development of genetic tools that can differentiate between reactivation and reinfection with a different strain of the disease. The maximum risk of advancement occurs during the first two years after the initial infection.⁸ The standard radiologic assessment for suspected or confirmed pulmonary tuberculosis is a chest X-ray. Although the radiological appearance of tuberculosis (TB) might vary, it is often highly typical.⁹ Calcified lumps or consolidation, uneven linear opacity, parenchymal bands, and pericatricial emphysema are among the CT features associated with inactive pulmonary tuberculosis.¹⁰ Computed tomography (CT) scans offer more precise information on the extent and distribution of pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB), since they reveal cavities and satellite lesions that are not visible on chest X-rays. This is due to the limits in the yield of chest X-ray in the diagnosis of PTB. Furthermore, CT can help differentiate between an active and an old illness. The pattern of HRCT results in active and inactive pulmonary tuberculosis, as well as the usefulness of high-resolution compute to forecast disease activity in pulmonary tuberculosis, were the main objectives of this study.¹¹

1. OBJECTIVES

To evaluate the role of High Resolution Computed Tomography in evaluation of disease activity in patients with pulmonary tuberculosis.

2. METHODOLOGY

Research Design: Cross sectional analytical study.

2. Clinical Settings: DHQ Hospital Hafizabad. 3.

Sample Size

$$n = (Z^2 * p * (1-p)) / d^2$$

$$P = 0.05 \quad Z =$$

$$95\% = 1.96 \quad d =$$

$$5\% \quad n = 55$$

3. **SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:** Convenient Sampling Technique.

Duration of Study: 4 Months after the approval of synopsis.

Inclusion Criteria

- A positive culture for Mycobacterium tuberculosis or sputum samples with positive acid-fast bacillus (AFB) staining are required for the diagnosis of pulmonary tuberculosis in participants.
- Before enrolling in the trial, participants must have gone at least one month without receiving any previous tuberculosis therapy, including antibiotics or anti-tuberculosis medications.
- Participants must give written informed consent and permission to have HRCT scans performed

Exclusion Criteria

- Pregnant women
- Patients who are not willing
- Patients that are uncooperative
- Patients diagnosed with lung cancer

4. Data Collection Procedure

Data sheets were used as data collecting techniques once an informed signed consent form was obtained. The factors of the questionnaire, which are listed below, were used to obtain the data. The participants' histories, complaints, and clinical diagnoses were recorded. Elements like age and gender. Participants were identified and recruited from the radiology department. The HRCT scans were performed and interpreted by radiologists.

The radiologist was interpreted HRCT scans for the presence of PTB and classify the type of PTB according to established criteria. Radiographic HRCT chest reports.

5. Data Analysis

SPSS version 29.0 was used to tabulate and analyses the data. Describing the data made use of descriptive statistics. The mean and standard deviation were provided as the outcome of quantity factors like age. Frequencies and percentages were used to report on qualitative factors like age. A bar graph was provided.

6. RESULTS

In this study, 55 individuals with pulmonary tuberculosis were diagnosed and several aspects from High-Resolution Computed Tomography (HRCT) were evaluated. The ensuing characteristics were examined for their existence and association. Consolidations are regions of heightened pulmonary parenchymal attenuation that obfuscate the boundaries of airways and veins. In 40% of the patients, consolidations were seen. Ill-Defined Nodules: Round, tiny opacities with a weak border that are found inside the lung parenchyma. 17% of the patients had ill-defined nodules. And off all the patients 38.2% showed tree in bud appearance. Granulomas with calcified centers are nodules that signify a

previously healed infection. Of the patients, 7% had calcified granulomas. Ground-Glass Opacities: Parts of the lung that exhibit unclear enhanced attenuation while maintaining vascular and bronchial characteristics. Among the patients, 7% had ground-glass opacities. Atelectasis: When a portion of the lung collapses completely or partially, there is less or no air in the alveoli. Of the patients, 7% had atelectasis. 21.8% patients have shown the feature of traction bronchiectasis. There were 25 female patients and 30 male patients in our study. Approximately 50 years old was the average age at presentation. It was discovered that the presence of trees in buds (38.2%), ill-defined nodules (30.9%), and consolidation (40%) had a strong predictive value for identifying disease activity. There were related findings: ground glass opacity (7%), atelectasis (7%), and traction bronchiectasis (12%). The results indicated inactive disease: calcified granulomas (7%) and atelectasis (7%).

Table 1 The age distribution information for each of the 55 patients are shown in the table. Patients range in age from 21 to 79 years old, with a minimum age of 21. The patients' average age is 50.41 years. An overview of the patient group's age distribution and average age is given in this summary.

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	55	21.00	79.00	50.4182	17.07792

Table 1.1 The gender distribution of 55 patients is shown in the table. Of the total, there are 25 patients (45.5%) who are female and 30 patients (54.5%) who are male. The proportion of male and female patients is easily seen by looking at the percentages.

	Frequency	Percent
Female	25	45.5
Male	30	54.5
Total	55	100.0

Figure 1 shows gender distribution

Table 1.2 shows statistics of all features.

Consolidations

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
NO	33	60.0	60.0	60.0
YES	22	40.0	40.0	100.0
Valid Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Figure 1.1 shows consolidations on HRCT

Figure 1.2 shows consolidations on HRCT

Table 1.4 The distribution of 55 patients is shown in the table according to the existence of the "tree in bud" look as detected by HRCT. Of the total patients, 21 patients (38.2%) did not have the "tree in bud" look, whereas 34 patients (61.8%) did. The percentages make it easy to see how many patients have the "tree in bud" look and how many do not.

Treeinbud

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
NO	34	61.8	61.8	61.8
YES	21	38.2	38.2	100.0
Valid Total	55	100.0	100.0	

Figure 1.3 shows tree in bud appearance on HRCT

Figure 1.4 shows tree in bud appearance on HRCT

DISCUSSION

One of the pathogenic viruses that causes tuberculosis is *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (TB). Tuberculosis is caused by bacteria, specifically *M. TB*, *M. Bovis*, *M. Microti*, *M. Africanum*, and *M. Canettii*. Those patients who showed up at the research site during the trial and received a TB diagnosis following a Tomography investigation

were enrolled. There were 30 male and 25 female patients in the current investigation. At the presentation, the average age was around 50.4 years old. Trees in buds, ill-defined nodules, and consolidation had a good prognostic value for diagnosing disease activity.

In an investigation by Dr. Pramod Kumar Dixit et al., HRCT showed that, in cases of active and

inactive tuberculosis, respectively, there were cavities in 32 and 11, consolidation in 12 and 17, tree-in-bud in 25 and 11, ill-defined nodules in 11 and 21, ground glass opacity in 8 and 30, atelectasis in 14 and 11, traction bronchiectasis in 12 and 23, peribronchial thickening in 11 and 45, and calcified granuloma in 42 and 23.¹²

There were related findings: ground glass opacity (7%), atelectasis (7%), traction bronchiectasis (12%). The results indicated inactive disease: calcified granulomas (7%) and atelectasis (7%). The findings showed atelectasis (7%) and calcified granulomas (7%) as inactive diseases. It is possible that these findings are not as specific indications of active tuberculosis because the presence of atelectasis (7%) and ground glass opacity (7%) was less predictive of disease activity. Additionally, the data show that patients with inactive illness were more likely to have calcified granulomas and atelectasis, and traction bronchiectasis which may imply that the lesions were healed or scarred from tuberculosis. Traction bronchiectasis, atelectasis, calcified granulomas, and peribronchial cuffing are markers of inactive illness, according to a research by Sumit Sharma et al. The results of HRCT can be used to evaluate the reversibility and activity of a disease. For example, the presence of ground glass opacities suggests a possibly reversible and active disease, while the presence of fibrotic opacities and septal thickening suggests an irreversible disease.¹³ According to our research, HRCT can be a helpful diagnostic tool for pulmonary tuberculosis disease activity, especially when paired with laboratory and clinical data. While calcified granulomas and atelectasis may suggest inactive illness, some radiological characteristics, such as trees in buds, ill-defined nodules, and consolidation, can aid in the identification of active disease. The results of this investigation have significant ramifications for pulmonary tuberculosis diagnosis and treatment. When the diagnosis is unclear, HRCT can be used as a diagnostic technique to help identify patients with active TB. HRCT can also be used to evaluate the efficacy of treatment and track disease activity over time. The research headed by Gulraiz Hikmatyar et al. When it comes to reliably diagnosing the

active PTB with strong sensitivity and specificity, HRCT is a dependable imaging technique. We believe that in suspected patients, HRCT can be utilized as a first-line imaging evaluation tool for PTB diagnosis.¹⁴

CONCLUSION

The HRCT has a higher sensitivity for distinguishing between active and inactive illness, it can be useful in both diagnosis and treatment. Consolidation, tree-in-bud look, and poorly defined nodules were the best markers of active illness. It was discovered that combining the indications increased the prediction value.

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